

ARTICLE

Analysis of Sound System Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction Mediated by Service Quality as an Intervening Variable at CV Liguori Abadi (Aiden Sound System Minahasa Utara)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of product quality on customer satisfaction, with service quality as a mediating variable, at CV Liguori Abadi. The population of this study were customers who rented audio devices at CV Liguori Abadi, with a sample of 200 respondents. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using the Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique. The results of the analysis show that product quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction, both directly and through service quality as a mediating variable. Service quality is also proven to have a significant effect on customer satisfaction, strengthening the relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction. The mediation of service quality strengthens the positive impact of product quality on satisfaction, indicating that good service can strengthen customers' positive perceptions of the products used. The implications of this study indicate that improving product and service quality simultaneously will help companies increase customer satisfaction and encourage the company's existence in the long term.

Keywords: Product Quality, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction

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Introduction

A service company, especially a Sound System business, must maintain the quality of the services offered above the competition and greater than what consumers imagine. The company must also understand what the needs and expectations of consumers are for the products or services offered. CV Liguori Abadi is one of the Sound System rental businesses since 2017, located in Treman Village, Kauditan District, North Minahasa Regency which continues to grow and fulfill consumer desires, which provides various Sound Systems for small to large events with various provisions of existing Sound System specifications. In ordering/booking, customers can directly come to CV Liguori Abadi to make a rental transaction which must provide a down payment as a deposit, then the customer will pay off the payment transaction after the Sound System is sent to the rental location.

A business can survive by implementing an effective strategy. Customer satisfaction is a key factor in maintaining and improving this business because satisfied customers are more likely to return to use the service and recommend it to others. Meanwhile, if the customer is not satisfied with the existing service, it can result in the customer not re-renting. What happened in CV Liguori was that there was still minimal service, for example, the inaccuracy of delivery time and reliability of the service provider that occurred because of the rental at the same time. In addition, seen from the quality of the existing products, CV Liguori Abadi still has devices that cannot be used properly, namely speakers whose sound is not clear to mics that still have problems in processing sound.

Product quality and service quality are important in the Sound System business world. The Sound System business is a business that continues to grow because basically the Sound System business is a very important business in various activities. This can be an opportunity for many entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs must innovate and must be able to read market opportunities and consumer behavior so that what consumers want and need can be met by Sound System business entrepreneurs. Competition between Sound System business actors is getting tighter by coming up with strategies that they do to attract customers.

To see customer satisfaction, business actors must prioritize and organize strategies so that the business can grow and run smoothly by providing the best quality of service and product quality which is the driving force for CV Liguori Abadi to achieve customer satisfaction. This customer satisfaction cannot be underestimated in the Sound System business world because good quality of service and product quality are very important for the continuity of a business activity.

Based on the description of the background of the problem above, the researcher is interested in conducting an in-depth study entitled "Analysis of Sound System Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction Mediated by Service Quality as an Intervening Variable at CV Liguori Abadi (Aiden Sound System Minahasa Utara)".

Research purposes

1. To analyze the influence of Sound System product quality on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi.
2. To analyze the influence of Sound System product quality on service quality at CV Liguori Abadi.
3. To analyze the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi.
4. To analyze the influence of service quality in mediating the relationship between Sound System product quality and customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi.

Literature Reviews

Marketing Management

Marketing management as the art and science of selecting target markets and acquiring, retaining, and growing customers through creating, delivering, and communicating superior customer value. Philip Kotler (1996) "Marketing is a social and managerial process by which individuals or groups obtain what they need and want through creating and exchanging products and values." Marketing is a social and managerial process about individuals or groups to get their needs and longing for to pass creation and barter product and value. "Marketing plays an important role in the company because the marketing department is directly related to consumers and other external environments of the company, the following are some definitions of marketing according to (Sudarsono, 2020) marketing is a managerial process that makes individuals or groups get what they want by creating, offering, and exchanging valuable products to other parties or all activities related to the delivery of products or services from producers to consumers. It is concluded that the marketing concept is a company/organization orientation that emphasizes that the main task of the company/organization is to determine the needs and wants of the market, and then fulfill those needs and wants so that customer satisfaction is achieved.

Consumer Behavior

Engel et al. (2022) stated that Consumer behavior is the act of obtaining, consuming, and using products and services. Mowen and Minor (2022) stated that Consumer behavior is a decision-making process that leads to the acquisition, consumption, and disposal of goods and services. Handoko (2019) argues that consumer behavior is an individual activity that is directly involved in obtaining and using goods and services including the decision-making process and preparation of determining these activities.

Based on the opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that consumer behavior is the act of obtaining, consuming and using products and services in which the consumer has a role in taking these actions.

Customer satisfaction

Kotler & Keller (2016) argue that customer satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing the performance (results) of a product that is thought of against the expected performance (or results). Customer satisfaction is influenced by the quality of service consisting of physical facilities (Tangibles), reliability (Reliability), responsiveness (Responsiveness), assurance (Assurance), and empathy (Empathy). If the quality of service is below expectations, then the customer is not satisfied, if the quality of service exceeds expectations, then the customer will feel satisfied or happy (Mowen and Minor, 2015) To create customer satisfaction, postal companies must create and manage a system to obtain many customers and have the ability to retain their customers.

Product Quality

A product is defined as anything that can be offered on the market and can satisfy consumer desires and needs, whether to be noticed, obtained, consumed or used (Kotler & Armstrong, 2020). Quality is the totality of the characteristics of a product that supports its ability to satisfy predetermined needs (Effendi, 2021). Each product has a different level of added value. There are five levels of products, namely the basic benefits of the product offered to consumers (core benefit), the basic form of a product that can be felt by the five senses (generic product), a series of product attributes and conditions expected by consumers when buying a product (expected product), something that distinguishes between the products offered by the company and the products offered by competitors, for example by adding various other benefits (equipped product) and all additions and changes in form experienced by a product

in the future (potential product) (Firmansyah MA, 2019).

Quality of Service

Lupiyoadi (2013: 197) explains that service quality is all activities that try to combine the value of ordering, processing to providing service results through communication to accelerate cooperation with customers. In short, the term service is a collaboration carried out by service providers with consumers. If the quality of service received by consumers is better or the same as imagined, then consumers tend to try again. However, if the service received is lower than the expected service, then consumers will be disappointed and will stop their relationship with the company concerned.

Service Quality Indicators

Kotler and Keller (2016) revealed that measuring service quality can use a number of indicators better known as the TERRA concept, including: Tangible, Empathy, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Assurance.

Rental

Renting or leasing is an agreement or agreement where one party undertakes to hand over an object to another party, so that this party can enjoy it for a certain period of time, which the latter party is able to pay for (Mardiana & Fatkhiyah, 2021). Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that renting is an agreement between two parties where one party lends an object to another party to be used for a certain period of time and the other party is able to pay the rental fee according to the agreement of both parties.

Previous research

Noor, Alhidayatullah, Amal (2023) in his research entitled Dimensions of Service Quality in Influencing Customer Satisfaction. Based on the results of the study, tangible evidence, dependability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy have a positive influence on consumer satisfaction.

Andri, Jasfar, Kristaung (2022) in a study entitled The Influence of Product Quality, Distribution and Service on Customer Loyalty Through Customer Satisfaction in the Indonesian Market. The results of the study show that there is a significant influence of product quality and service quality on customer satisfaction.

Wanlapa Panket and Tosaporn Mahamud (2024) in this study entitled Service Quality Affecting Customer Satisfaction of Cabrik Company (Thailand) Co., Ltd. The results of the study show that service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction.

Syifa Nur Febriani (2023) in her research entitled Analysis of the Influence of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction at the Mayoutfit Fashion Store, Bandung Branch, Indonesia. The results of the study show that there is a significant influence between product quality and customer satisfaction.

Research Model and Hypothesis

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Results of Theoretical and Empirical Studies, 2024

Hypothesis

H1: Product Quality is suspected to have a direct influence on Customer Satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi

H2: Product Quality is suspected to have a direct influence on Service Quality at CV Liguori Abadi

H3: Service Quality is suspected to have a direct influence on Customer Satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi

H4: Service Quality is suspected to mediate the relationship between Product Quality and Customer Satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi

Methodology

This research is field research. According to Dedy Mulyana, field research is a type of research that studies phenomena in their natural environment. For that, the primary data is data that comes from the field. So that the data obtained is truly in accordance with the reality of the phenomena that exist at the research location. The approach used in this study is a quantitative approach that emphasizes numerical data (numbers) processed using statistical methods.

Location and Place of Research

The location used as a research site is at CV Liguori Abadi, Treman Village, Kauditan District, North Minahasa Regency.

Method of collecting data

The data collection technique used is through a questionnaire. In this study, the questionnaire was submitted to respondents, namely customers. CV Liguori Abadi. The data used is primary data. The primary data in this study is data obtained directly from the field through data from questionnaires distributed directly to CV Liguori Abadi customers.

Population and Research Sample

Purposive sampling was used in this study. Purposive sampling is a technique for collecting data samples from data sources with several considerations such as people who are considered to understand something, can be trusted or people who have the authority that will make it easier for researchers to explore certain objects or social situations. (Sugiyono, 2018). The population in this study were all customers of CV Liguori Abadi as many as 200 people.

Data analysis

Data analysis in this study, using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS) or abbreviated as SEM - PLS. SEM - PLS is a statistical technique used to analyze the relationship between latent variables through measured indicators. PLS-SEM is very useful for complex models with the aim of predicting dependent variables (Hair, et al., 2022).

Research Instruments

This study uses an instrument scale that is commonly used in quantitative research, namely the Likert scale. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) the Likert Scale is a tool used to develop instruments used to measure the attitudes, perceptions, and opinions of a person or group of people towards the potential and problems of an object, the design of a product, a process create products and products that have been developed or created". Before analyzing the data, the research instrument was tested first.

Results and Discussion

Research result

Model Development

Figure 2. Research Model Development

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

This model illustrates how product quality and service quality work synergistically in influencing customer satisfaction. Good product quality directly influences customer satisfaction, but service quality acts as a mediating variable that strengthens the effect. This means that although product quality plays an important role, a good service experience greatly helps improve customer perceptions of the product itself.

Outer Model

Convergent Validity

The following table presents the results of the convergent validity analysis using outer loading to measure the validity of each indicator in each variable in this study:

Table 1. Convergent Validity Test Results

Indicator	Measurement Item	Outer Loading	Status	
Product Quality	Form	KPR1.1	0.672	Valid
		KPR1.2	0.671	Valid
Features		KPR2.1	0.801	Valid
		KPR2.2	0.777	Valid
Performance Quality		KPR3.1	0.748	Valid
		KPR3.2	0.752	Valid

Conformance Quality	KPR4.1	0.768	Valid
	KPR4.2	0.793	Valid
Durability	KPR5.1	0.822	Valid
	KPR5.2	0.764	Valid
Reliability	KPR6.1	0.826	Valid
	KPR6.2	0.783	Valid
Repairability	KPR7.1	0.817	Valid
	KPR7.2	0.787	Valid
Style	KPR8.1	0.778	Valid
	KPR8.2	0.703	Valid
Customizability.	KPR9.1	0.762	Valid
	KPR9.2	0.735	Valid
Customer satisfaction			
Expectancy			
Confirmation/Disconfirmation	KPE1.1	0.778	Valid
	KPE1.2	0.648	Valid
Need Fulfillment	KPE2.1	0.781	Valid
	KPE2.2	0.851	Valid
Quality	KPE3.1	0.807	Valid
	KPE3.2	0.827	Valid
Value	KPE4.1	0.743	Valid
	KPE4.2	0.801	Valid
Equity/Inequity	KPE5.1	0.844	Valid
	KPE5.2	0.839	Valid
Regret/Unregret	KPE6.1	0.839	Valid
	KPE6.2	0.830	Valid
Unappreciated Cognition.	KPE7.1	0.830	Valid
	KPE7.2	0.759	Valid
Quality of Service			
Tangible	KL1.1	0.757	Valid
	KL1.2	0.808	Valid
Empathy	KL2.1	0.822	Valid
	KL2.2	0.790	Valid
Reliability	KL3.1	0.744	Valid
	KL3.2	0.753	Valid
Responsiveness	KL4.1	0.799	Valid
	KL4.2	0.825	Valid
Assurance	KL5.1	0.789	Valid
	KL5.2	0.779	Valid

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Based on the table above, the outer loading results show that most of the indicators in the model have a value of more than 0.7, which indicates good convergent validity. In general, an indicator is declared valid if its outer loading value is greater than 0.7, according to the guidelines from Hair et al. (2022). However, there are several indicators with values between 0.4 and 0.7, such as KPR1.1 (0.672), KPR1.2 (0.671), and KPE1.2 (0.648). The outer loading value in the range of 0.4 to 0.7 is still considered valid because the final decision regarding convergent validity is not only based on outer loading, but also takes into account the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability

(CR) values. If both of these values are above the predetermined threshold, then indicators with outer loading below 0.7 can still be declared valid.

Discriminant Validity

The following table presents the results of discriminant validity testing using the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio between product quality, service quality, and customer satisfaction variables:

Table 2. Results of Discriminant Validity Test

	Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)
Service Quality (Z) <-> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.857
Product Quality (X) <-> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.846
Product Quality (X) <-> Service Quality (Z)	0.848

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Discriminant validity in this study was tested using the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio, which is used to evaluate the extent to which different variables can actually be distinguished from each other. Based on the table above, the HTMT values for all pairs of variables are all below the threshold of 0.90 as recommended by Hair et al. (2022).

Reliability (Composite Reliability, Cronbach Alpha, & AVE)

The following table presents the results of reliability tests using Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability (rho_a and rho_c), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for the variables product quality, service quality, and customer satisfaction:

Table 3. Reliability Test Results (Composite Reliability, Cronbach Alpha, & AVE)

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance Extracted (AVE)
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.956	0.958	0.961	0.640
Service Quality (Z)	0.932	0.932	0.942	0.619
Product Quality (X)	0.958	0.960	0.962	0.586

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Based on the table above, the results of the reliability test show that all variables in this study have a very good level of reliability. Cronbach's alpha for the three variables is above the threshold value of 0.7, which indicates that all measurement items for each variable have strong internal consistency. The rho_c (Composite Reliability) value for each variable is above the recommended threshold of 0.7, even approaching or exceeding 0.96 for product quality and customer satisfaction. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each variable is also above the minimum threshold value of 0.5,

suggested by Hair et al. (2022). The AVE for product quality (X) is 0.586, which means that more than 58% of the indicator variance is successfully explained by the construct. Likewise, the AVE for customer satisfaction (Y) and service quality (Z) are 0.640 and 0.619, respectively, indicating that the explained variance is quite significant, more than 60%.

Multicollinearity (VIF)

The following table shows the results of the multicollinearity test using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for each indicator in the research model:

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results (VIF)

Item	VIF	Item	VIF	Item	VIF	Item	VIF
KPR1.1	2,2	KPR6.2	3,4	KL3.1	3,1	KPE3.2	3,8
KPR1.2	2,1	KPR7.1	3,2	KL3.2	3,5	KPE4.1	2,1
KPR2.1	3,1	KPR7.2	2,8	KL4.1	2,4	KPE4.2	3,1
KPR2.2	3,3	KPR8.1	2,6	KL4.2	3,4	KPE5.1	3,9
KPR3.1	2,4	KPR8.2	2,5	KL5.1	3,0	KPE5.2	3,9
KPR3.2	2,4	KPR9.1	3,4	KL5.2	2,9	KPE6.1	4,3
KPR4.1	2,7	KPR9.2	2,3	KPE1.1	2,4	KPE6.2	4,0
KPR4.2	3,0	KL1.1	2,1	KPE1.2	1,8	KPE7.1	3,1
KPR5.1	3,5	KL1.2	2,9	KPE2.1	2,9	KPE7.2	2,4
KPR5.2	2,3	KL2.1	3,5	KPE2.2	3,8		
KPR6.1	3,9	KL2.2	2,8	KPE3.1	2,7		

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Multicollinearity test was conducted to ensure that there is no strong linear relationship between the indicators used in the research model. Based on the table above, all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for each indicator are below the threshold of 5, as suggested by Hair et al. (2019). This indicates that the model is free from significant multicollinearity problems.

Model Power (R Square)

The following table presents the results of the model strength test using the R-square and adjusted R-square values for the service quality and customer satisfaction variables:

Table 5. Model Strength Test Results (R Square)

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.733	0.730
Quality of Service (Z)	0.650	0.649

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Based on the table above, the R-square value for the customer satisfaction variable (Y) is 0.733, which means that around 73.3% of the variance in customer satisfaction can be explained by product quality and service quality. With an R-square value of this size, this model is categorized as a strong model, according to the guidelines provided by Hair et al. (2019), where an R-square value above 0.75 indicates high predictive power.

Goodness of FIT

The following table presents the results of the Goodness of Fit test for the research model using various components such as SRMR, d_ULS, d_G, Chi-square, and NFI:

Table 6. Goodness of FIT Test Results

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.059	0.059
d_ULS	3.171	3.171
d_G	2.155	2.155
Chi-square	2086.92	2086.92
NFI	0.744	0.744

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

One of the main indicators used is the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), which shows a value of 0.059 for both the saturated and estimated models. Other indicators such as d_ULS (3.171) and d_G (2.155) describe the distance between the saturated model and the estimated model. The Chi-square obtained at 2086.92 is also interpreted as part of the model fit test, although in more complex models, large Chi-square values often do not fully reflect model misfit, especially if the sample size is large. The Normed Fit Index (NFI) of 0.744 indicates that this model has a fairly good level of fit, although not perfect. The NFI measures how well the estimated model can be compared to the null model (a model with no relationship between variables). An NFI value close to 1 indicates a good fit, and with a value of 0.744, this model shows an adequate level of fit.

Effect Size (F Square)

The following table presents the results of the Effect Size (f-square) measurement to identify the magnitude of the influence of the product quality variable on customer satisfaction and service quality as a mediating variable:

Table 7. Effect Size Test Results (F Square)

	f-square
Service Quality (Z) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.252863
Product Quality (X) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.279346
Product Quality (X) -> Service Quality (Z)	1.860306

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

The results of the Effect Size or f-square measurement in the table above show how much influence each independent variable has on the dependent variable in the research model. Which shows that service quality makes a significant contribution to increasing customer satisfaction, although it is not a dominant factor, product quality plays a fairly important role in shaping customer satisfaction, however, its contribution to satisfaction is not greater than the total influence of service quality and product quality has a very strong influence on service quality.

Estimation Accuracy (Q Square)

The following table presents the results of measuring the accuracy of the estimation using the Q-square (Q²) value for the variables product quality, service quality, and customer satisfaction:

Table 8. Results of Estimation Accuracy Test (Q Square)

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	2800.000	1512.814	0.460
Quality of Service (Z)	2000.000	1207.187	0.396

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Based on the table above, the Q-square (Q²) value is used to measure the prediction accuracy of the developed model. A positive Q² value indicates that the model has a relatively accurate prediction ability for the dependent variable. For the customer satisfaction variable (Y), the Q² value is 0.460, which indicates that this value shows a good level of estimation accuracy, where the model is able to predict quite accurately how these factors affect customer satisfaction. For the service quality variable (Z), the Q² value of 0.396 indicates that the model also has a fairly good prediction ability in explaining variance in service quality. With a Q² value approaching 0.4, this model shows that almost 40% of the variation in service quality can be explained by product quality. This shows that product quality plays a significant role in influencing customer perceptions of the quality of service they receive.

Inner Model

The following table presents the results of hypothesis testing to measure the direct, indirect, and total influence between the variables of product quality, service quality, and customer satisfaction, along with the path coefficient values, t-statistics, and p-values as the basis for making decisions on whether or not the influence is significant:

Table 9. Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Direct Effect					
Service Quality (Z) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.439	0.461	0.112	3.920	0.000
Product Quality (X) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.462	0.441	0.112	4.121	0.000
Product Quality (X) -> Service Quality (Z)	0.806	0.808	0.051	15,775	0.000
Indirect Effect					
Product Quality (X) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.354	0.376	0.107	3.308	0.001
Total Effect					
Service Quality (Z) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.439	0.461	0.112	3.920	0.000
Product Quality (X) -> Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.816	0.818	0.027	30,399	0.000
Product Quality (X) -> Service Quality (Z)	0.806	0.808	0.051	15,775	0.000

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing presented in the table, several direct, indirect, and total influences between the variables in this research model were analyzed to understand the strength of the relationship between the variables.

The relationship between service quality (Z) and customer satisfaction (Y) has a path coefficient of 0.439 with a t-statistics value of 3.920 and a p-value of 0.000. This shows that service quality has a significant direct influence on customer satisfaction.

The relationship between product quality (X) and customer satisfaction (Y) shows a path coefficient of 0.462 with a t-statistics value of 4.121 and a p-value of 0.000, which also shows a significant effect. This means that product quality has a significant direct effect on customer satisfaction.

The relationship between product quality (X) and service quality (Z) was also tested, with a path coefficient of 0.806, t-statistics of 15.775, and a p-value of 0.000. These results indicate that product quality has a very significant direct influence on service quality.

In the indirect effect, the relationship between product quality (X) and customer satisfaction (Y) through service quality (Z) shows a path coefficient of 0.354 with a t-statistics value of 3.308 and a p-value of 0.001. These results indicate that service quality plays a significant mediator role in the relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction.

Product quality (X) on customer satisfaction (Y), the total coefficient increased to 0.816 with a t-statistics value of 30.399 and a p-value of 0.000. This shows that the total influence of product quality on customer satisfaction is very strong, and most of this influence is mediated by service quality.

Product Quality Towards Customer Satisfaction

The results of the study indicate that product quality has a significant influence on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi. This influence is formed through a series of indicators that represent dimensions of product quality, such as performance quality, conformance quality, durability, reliability, and features. Customers who rent audio equipment from CV Liguori Abadi rely heavily on product quality to ensure that the events they organize run smoothly without technical disruptions. This finding is in line with previous studies that also emphasize the importance of product quality in shaping customer satisfaction, such as the findings of Raja, Maharani, and Raja (2023) that product quality significantly contributes to customer satisfaction, with customers who are satisfied with product quality tending to make repeat purchases.

Product Quality Against Service Quality

The results of this study indicate that product quality has a significant influence on service quality at CV Liguori Abadi. As an audio equipment rental service provider, the quality of the products offered, such as the reliability and durability of sound system devices, are the main factors that influence customer perceptions of service quality. In the context of the rental business, high-quality products that meet customer technical expectations provide a strong foundation for the quality of service provided. This finding is supported by several previous studies which also show that product quality has a

significant effect on service quality. Ramadhan and Sari (2024) stated that good product quality creates a positive perception in the minds of customers, which ultimately influences their assessment of service quality.

Quality of Service Towards Customer Satisfaction

The results of this study indicate that service quality has a significant influence on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi. As a company engaged in the rental of audio equipment, the quality of service provided to customers includes various aspects, such as reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and professionalism of the team in installing and maintaining equipment. This finding is supported by several previous studies. Raja, Maharani, and Raja (2023) emphasized that although the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction is not as great as product quality, good service still plays a role in strengthening the overall customer experience.

Product Quality Towards Customer Satisfaction Through Service Quality

The results of the study indicate that service quality significantly mediates the effect of product quality on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi. In the context of the audio equipment rental business, product quality is the main foundation in creating customer satisfaction, but service quality plays a key role in strengthening this influence. This finding is supported by research by Maulidiah, Survival, and Budiantono (2023) which emphasizes that service quality plays an important mediator in the influence of product quality on customer satisfaction

Conclusions

1. Product quality has a significant influence on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi.
2. Product quality has been proven to have a significant influence on the quality of service felt by CV Liguori Abadi customers.
3. Service quality plays an important role in shaping CV Liguori Abadi's customer satisfaction.
4. Service quality significantly mediates the effect of product quality on customer satisfaction at CV Liguori Abadi.

Suggestion

1. CV Liguori Abadi is advised to continue to improve the quality of the products rented, especially in terms of reliability, performance, and durability of audio devices. Performing routine maintenance, updating obsolete devices, and adding product variations with the latest technology can help maintain a high level of customer satisfaction. The company can also conduct periodic evaluations of frequently used devices to ensure that product quality remains consistent.
2. CV Liguori Abadi is advised to strengthen the quality of service provided to customers, especially in terms of responsiveness, empathy, and timeliness. Training for staff to improve communication and service skills can help improve the overall

customer experience. In addition, the company can consider adding additional service features, such as technical monitoring during the event, to provide a greater sense of security for customers.

3. For researchers who want to follow up on the findings of this study, it is recommended to conduct research by expanding other variables that can affect customer satisfaction, such as price, sales promotion, perceived value, and so on. In addition, researchers can also further examine the mediating role of other variables that may have an effect, such as customer loyalty, to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that affect customer satisfaction in the context of audio equipment rental.

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